

Liquid chromatography–tadem mass spectrometry reveals the presence of flavonoid-glycosides in honey, and their potential as floral-origin markers

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Abstract

HPLC-MS-MS analysis of unifloral honey extracts has shown the presence of flavonoid glycosides in most of the analysed samples. These compounds are not present in large amounts, but can amount up to 600 µg/100g honey in canola and rapeseed honeys. Rhamnosyl-hexosides (rutinosides and neohesperidosides) and dihexosides (sophorosides and gentiobiosides) of flavonols such as quercetin, kaempferol, isorhamnetin and 8-methoxykaempferol, are the main flavonoid glycosides found. However, flavonoid triglycosides and mono-glycosides are also detected in some floral origins. Eucalyptus and orange blossom nectars were also analysed showing that nectar flavonoid glucosides, as is the case of eucalyptus flavonoids, can be readily hydrolysed by the bee saliva enzymes, while flavonoid rhamnosyl-glucosides, as is the case of citrus nectar flavonoids, are not hydrolysed, and by these reason the flavonoid glycoside content of citrus honey is higher than that of eucalyptus honey that contains mainly aglycones. These results show that the HPLC-MSn analysis of flavonoid glycosides in honey is a promising analytical method for the objective determination of the floral origin of unifloral honeys.

Keywords: Honey; Flavonoid glycosides; Floral origin markers; HPLC-MS

1. Introduction

Honey phytochemical composition depends on its floral origin, the contamination with propolis, a plant resin collected by bees for different purposes within the hive, and the type of honeybee subspecies. In addition, external factors such as climate, geographical origin and processing conditions can also affect honey phytochemicals composition. Unifloral honeys are appreciated by the consumers as they are considered higher quality products with characteristic sensory properties. Unifloral honey production is, however, limited. For this reason, the objective determination of the floral origin of honeys has become a very important issue regarding honey quality.

The traditional technique used to identify honey botanical origin is the melissopalynological method (EU Council Directive 2001/110). However, several new analytical methodologies have been recently explored to help with the determination of both the botanical and geographical origins. These include gas chromatography (GC) [1], capillary electrophoresis (CE) [2-4] and HPLC-PAD [5-8]. In particular, HPLC-PAD allows the identification of different phytochemical compounds that can be used as botanical markers for the identification of the honey floral origin [9,10]. Currently, specific phytochemicals can be related to the floral origin of several honeys as is the case of kaempferol for rosemary honey [11], ellagic acid, benzoic acid, phenylacetic acid, mandelic acid and β -phenylactic acid for heather honey [12,13], abscisic acid for calluna and heather honeys [14], methyl syringate for manuka honey [15], kynurenic acid and 3-aminoacetophenone and 1-phenyl-ethanol for chestnut honey [16,17], terpenoid acids for linden honey [18], myricetin, tricetin and luteolin for eucalyptus honey [19,20] and hesperetin for citrus honey [21]. These metabolites are generally lipophilic and bee saliva enzymes have been suggested as the responsible for the transformation of the polar phytochemicals present in floral nectar into the metabolites

detected in honey. A recent study has demonstrated the occurrence of kaempferol rhamnosides and rhamnosyl-glucosides in acacia honey [22] and indicated the inability of bee enzymes to hydrolyze specific glycosidic combinations present in plant nectars, as is the case of rhamnosides and rutinosides. This finding enlarged considerably the potential number of floral markers for the botanical origin of honey. Previous studies of honey phytochemicals were addressed to the study of lipophilic metabolites (flavonoid aglycones, terpenoids, alkaloids) while the occurrence of glycosidic phytochemicals had been neglected. With the development of HPLC-MSn equipments, the detection and identification of small amounts of glycosidic phytochemicals in a complex food matrix as honey has become possible. The present study aims to the determination of flavonoid glycosides in unifloral honeys, using HPLC-MSn. In some cases, the floral nectars have also been studied in order to evaluate the metabolic changes occurring during bee manufacturing and honey maturation, and to evaluate the suitability of these phytochemicals as potential markers of honey floral origin.

2. Experimental

3.1. Honey collection

Twenty seven experimental and commercial honey samples from 12 different floral origins and produced in different localities of Italy, Slovakia and Spain were selected for this study. Experimental honeys were provided and certified by the Agricultural Research Council (CRA-API, Bologna, Italy) and the Institute of Molecular Biology (Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia). Commercial honeys used for this study were purchased in a local supermarket (Table 1). All samples were stored at 4 °C in dark until analysis. The botanical origin was certified by the traditional analyses: sensory and pollen analyses and physicochemical analyses.

3.2. Nectar collection

Eucalyptus blossom nectar

Eucalyptus blossoms were collected in Espinardo (Murcia, Spain) during June 2007. Eucalyptus nectar has a high density and it remains in the lower parts of the pistil, inside the shaft. To obtain the nectar, the stamens were removed using forceps, leaving only the shaft of the pistil. Then, one drop of Milli-Q water was placed in and recovered together with the nectar using a Pasteur pipette. The nectar was kept in an eppendorf test-tube and stored at -20 °C until analysis.

Orange blossom nectar

Orange floral nectar was collected in Santomera (Murcia, Spain) in spring 2007. The droplets of nectar from orange blossoms, situated in the concave sepals, were aspirated using a glass capillary, then collected in eppendorf test tubes and stored at -20 °C until analysis

3.3. Extraction of phytochemicals from nectar.

Phytochemical compounds of eucalyptus, and orange nectars were extracted using a solid phase extraction (SPE) cartridge (a Sep-Pak reversed phase C₁₈ cartridge; Waters Milipore, USA). Nectar samples were diluted with ultra pure water (Milli-Q system, Millipore Corp., Bedford, MA), and centrifuged at 7000 *rpm* for 10 min, in a Centromix centrifuge (Selecta, Barcelona). The supernatants were filtered through a SPE cartridge previously activated with methanol (10 mL) followed by water (10 mL). Then, the phytochemicals that remained adsorbed in the cartridge were eluted with 1 mL methanol. The methanol extracts were filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter

Millex-HV₁₃ (Millipore Corp., USA) and stored at -20°C until further analysis by HPLC-PAD-MSn.

3.4. *Extraction of phytochemicals from honey.*

Honey samples (10g) were dissolved with five parts of water (adjusted to pH 2 with HCl) until completely fluid. This solution (50 mL) was then filtered through a Sep-Pak C₁₈ cartridge, which was previously activated as described above. The cartridge was washed with 10 mL water and the phytochemical compounds eluted with 2 mL methanol. The methanol fraction was filtered through a 0.45- μ m filter and stored at -20 °C until further analyzed by HPLC-DAD-MS-MS.

3.5. *HPLC-PAD-Tandem Mass Spectrometry (MSn)*

Chromatographic separations of eucalyptus and orange nectars were carried out a C₁₈ LiChroCART column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (RP-18 , 250x4 mm; 5 μ m particle size) protected with a 4x4 mm C₁₈ LiChroCART guard column, with 1% acetic acid (A) and methanol (B) as solvents (99.9%, HPLC grade; Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Starting with 20 % B, to reach 50 % B at 40 min, 80 % B at 55 min, and then became isocratic for 5 min.

Analysis of phytochemical compounds of honey samples was achieved with the same instrument, and on the same column used in nectar analyses. In this case, the mobile phase used was water/formic acid (99:1, v/v) (solvent A) and HPLC grade methanol (solvent B) (99.9%, HPLC grade; Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and the elution was performed with a gradient starting with 10 % B to reach 30 % B at 20 min, 45 % B at 30 min, 60% B at 40 min, 70% B at 45 min, 90% B at 60 min and then

became isocratic for 5 min. The flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹ and all chromatograms were recorded at 290, 320, 340 and 360 nm.

The HPLC system was equipped with an Agilent 1100 Series diode array and a mass detector in series (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). The HPLC system consisted of a binary pump (G1312 A), an auto sampler (G1313 A) a degasser (G1322 A), and photodiode-array detector (G1315 B) controlled by software (v. A08.03). The mass detector was an ion trap spectrometer (G2445A) equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) system and controlled by software (v. 4.1). The nebulizer gas was nitrogen; the pressure and the flow rate of the dryer gas were set at 65 psi and 11L min⁻¹ respectively. The full scan mass covered the range from *m/z* 100–1000. Collision-induced fragmentation experiments were performed in the ion trap using helium as collision gas, with voltage ramping cycles from 0.3 up to 2 V. The heated capillary and voltage were maintained at 350° C and 4 kV, respectively. Mass spectrometry data were acquired in the negative mode. The phenolic compounds were identified according to their UV spectra, molecular weights, retention times and their MS_n fragments, and whenever possible, by chromatographic comparisons with authentic standards. Flavonols, flavones and flavanonas were quantified as quercetin, chrysin and hesperetin at 340 nm and 290nm respectively. Flavonoids glycosides were quantificated as rutin at 340nm. Calibration curves were prepared for the UV detector. The calibration curves were linear in the range of 5-500 μM for rutin and were characterized by correlation coefficients of >0.99. The limit of detection was 0.61 μg/L, and the limit of quantification was 1.52 μg/L. Quercetin, rutin and hesperidin was purchased from Sigma (St. Louis MO) and chrysin from Carl Roth OGH (Karlsruhe, Germany). The results were expressed as micrograms per 100 g of honey.

3. Results

3.1. HPLC-MS-MS analyses of flavonoid glycosides in unifloral honeys.

The HPLC-PAD-MSn study of the extracts obtained from unifloral honeys of different botanical origins (Table 1) revealed the presence of different flavonoid glycosides of quercetin (3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone; [aglycone-H]⁻ fragment at m/z 301); kaempferol (3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxyflavone, m/z 285), 8-methoxykaempferol (3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methoxyflavone, m/z 315) and isorhamnetin (3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-3'-methoxyflavone, m/z 315). The occurrence of flavonol triglycosides (**1**, **14-17**) and flavonol diglycosides (**2-13**) was detected in different honey samples (Fig. 1). In addition the flavanone hesperetin 7-rutinoside (hesperidin) (**11**) was found in citrus honey. These compounds are generally minor constituents in the HPLC chromatograms, while hydroxycinnamates derived from propolis were the main constituents (Fig. 1). Flavonoid aglycones characteristic of propolis (chrysin, galangin, pinocembrin, pinobanksin and quercetin and kaempferol methyl ethers) were also detected generally in higher proportions than the flavonoid glycosides (data not shown).

HPLC-MSn analysis can be used to establish the nature of the sugars, the interglycosidic linkage and the position of glycosylation in flavonoid glycosides [21]. The analysis of the available samples revealed the occurrence in honeys of flavonoid hexosyl (1→2) hexosides (tentatively sophorosides), rhamnosyl (1→2) hexosides (tentatively neohesperidosides), rhamnosyl(1→6)hexosides (tentatively rutinosides), hexosyl (1→6) hexosides (tentatively gentiobiosides), and pentosides, hexosides and rhamnosides depending on the floral origin of the honey sample analysed. The flavonoid triglycosides had always a similar glycosylation patters with glycosidic substitutions at the hydroxyls in the 3- and 7-positions of the flavonoid nucleus. The MS²[M-H]⁻ spectra of these compounds was characterized by the presence of only one

ion as a result of the loss of the glycosyl residue in position 7 [M-H-Gly]⁻, that it is known to be released first than the glycosyl residue at 3-position, during the MS fragmentation [23]. In compounds **1** and **14**, the glycosidic residue at 7 position was a hexosyl residue as a relevant ([M-H-162]⁻) ion was observed, and in compounds **15-17** the glycosidic fraction at position 7 was a deoxyhexosyl residue (most likely rhamnose) as a relevant ([M-H-146]⁻) ion was observed instead (Table 2).

In all the triglycosides studied, with the exception of compound **16**, the MS3 event [(M-H)→(M-H-Gly7)]⁻ showed that the fragmentation of the glycosidic fraction in the position 3 of the aglycone produced only one ion corresponding to the deprotonated aglycone [Aglc-H]⁻ (Table 2). The absence of other fragment ions as [M-H-162]⁻ and/or [M-H-180]⁻, indicates for all these compounds an interglycosidic linkage (1→6). However, the fragmentation of **16** showed an intermediate ion [(M-H)-162]⁻ suggesting that in this case the interglycosidic linkage is (1→2) (hexosyl(1→2)hexose) and most probably sophorose [23].

The MS2[M-H]⁻ and MS3[(M-H)→(M-H-Gly7)]⁻ fragmentations of the honey diglycosides and triglycosides, showed in several cases a base peak corresponding to the deprotonated aglycone ion [Aglc-H]⁻ (Table 2) at *m/z* 315 corresponding to a tetrahydroxy-monomethoxyflavone. These flavonol aglycones were identified either as isorhamnetin (**1**, **7**, **9**, **13** and **14**) or 8-methoxykaempferol (**4** and **5**) as the spectra of the 8-methoxykaempferol derivatives showed a characteristic ion [M-H-15]⁻ and this ion was not detected in the case of isorhamnetin derivatives. This could be explained by an easier loss of the methyl ether on the hydroxyl at 8 position than that at the hydroxyl at the 3' position. In addition, compound **4** has been tentatively identified as 8-methoxykaempferol-3-*O*-sophoroside by direct chromatographic comparison with an authentic marker previously isolated and identified from almond pollen [24]. For other

flavonoids a characteristic fragment ion at m/z 301 (pentahydroxyflavone or trihydroxy-methoxyflavanone) revealed that the flavonoid was a quercetin glycoside (**2**, **10** and **15**) or a hesperetin glycoside (**11**) and they were readily identified by the characteristic UV spectra of the flavanone (hesperetin) that is very different from that of flavonols (quercetin) [25]. In other flavonoids a fragment ion at m/z 285 (tetrahydroxyflavone), together with a characteristic UV spectrum of flavonols, indicated that the glycoside was a derivative of kaempferol (**3**, **6**, **8**, **12**, **16**, and **17**) (Table 2).

In the MS²[M-H]⁻ of the honey flavonoid diglycosides **2** and **4-9**, abundant ions corresponding to the loss of the terminal sugar and/or terminal sugar + H₂O were observed, which indicate that the interglycosidic linkage should be 1→2, either with a hexosyl residue [M-H-162]⁻/[M-H-180]⁻ or a rhamnosyl residue [(M-H)-146]⁻/[(M-H)-164]⁻) as terminal sugars. Thus, compounds **2**, **4**, **6** and **7** should be tentatively identified as flavonoid hexosyl(1→2)hexosides (tentatively sophorosides; glucosyl(1→2)glucosides), and **5**, **8** and **9** as flavonoid rhamnosyl(1→2)hexosides (tentatively neohesperidosides; rhamnosyl(1→2)glucosides). These ions were not observed in compounds **10**, **11** and **12** which indicated the presence of a interglycosidic linkage 1→6 either a rhamnosyl (1→6) hexoside (tentatively rutinoside; rhamnosyl (1→6) glucoside), or a hexosyl(1→6) hexoside (tentatively a gentiobioside; glucosyl (1→6) glucoside) in the case of compound **13** [23].

In the MS/MS analysis of **3** (an isomer of compound **6**, kaempferol 3-sophoroside) a high abundance of the ion [M-H-162]⁻ was observed, but in this case the fragment ion [M-H-180]⁻ was not detected this being a clear difference with the fragmentation of compound **6**. This suggested that compound **3** should be identified either as an isomeric kaempferol-3-*O*-dihexoside (with different hexoses) or a kaempferol-di-*O*-hexoside. This should be most likely identified as kaempferol-3, 4'-di-

O-hexoside as the fragmentation of kaempferol-3,7-di-*O*-glucoside shows as base peak the ion [M-H-162]⁻ [21] and this fragment was not present here.

3.2. *Distribution of flavonoid glycosides in unifloral honeys.*

The flavonoid glycoside profiles of the analysed honeys are shown in Fig. 1. Flavonoid glycosides were detected in all the samples analysed with the exception of eucalyptus sample (Eucalyptus 2) and lavender. The amount of these compounds, quantified as rutin (quercetin 3-rutinoside), ranged between 8 and 408 µg/100g (Table 3), and some samples contained traces of glycosides that were detected but could not be quantified in the UV chromatogram. The total amount of flavonoid glycosides ranged 0-600 µg/100g honey, with canola and rapeseed being those honeys with higher flavonoid glycoside content. The largest amounts found were similar to those previously reported in robinia (acacia) honey [22]. The available *Brassicaceae* honeys (canola and rapeseed) were those containing more flavonoid glycosides both in number and total quantity. Thus, seven different flavonoid glycosides were detected in canola honey and nine in rapeseed honey (Table 3). Both canola and rapeseed belong to *Brassica napus*, but they are different cultivars. Both have in common the occurrence of a high number of glycosides but differ in the type of glycosides found. Consistent flavonoid glycoside composition was detected in tilia, taraxacum, rosemary, lucerne, linden and cherry blossom honeys. Of other unifloral origins, only one honey sample was available for analysis, and therefore the glycosides found could not be associated to the floral origin. Some more honeys samples of canola, rapeseed, rhododendrom and sunflower honey should be analysed in the future to confirm the flavonoid profiles detected as potential floral origin markers.

Two isorhamnetin triglycosides were detected in the honeys samples analysed. One was tentatively identified as isorhamnetin-3-*O*-pentosylglucoside-7-*O*-glucoside (**1**), present only in one of the taraxacum honey samples (taraxacum 1). The other (compound **14**, isorhamnetin 3-*O*-rutinoside-7-*O*-hexoside) was only detected in both samples of lucerne honey, and this could be a potential marker for this floral origin. Compound **15** (quercetin 3-*O*-rutinoside-7-*O*-rhamnoside) was the main flavonol glycoside detected in canola honey and was not detected in any other samples analysed. However, the kaempferol triglycosides **16** and **17**, were both detected in canola and rapeseed honeys, which reflects that both honeys are of close floral origin, while **16** alone was detected in cherry blossom, taraxacum and rosemary honey samples.

The characterized flavonoid diglycosides were derivatives of quercetin, kaempferol, 8-methoxykaempferol, isorhamnetin and the flavanone hesperetin (**11**). Hesperetin 7-rutinoside (**11**) was only detected in rosemary and orange honeys (Fig.1; Table 3). In a previous study, hesperetin had been suggested as a suitable marker for the floral origin of citrus honey, and this was due to the presence of hesperetin 7-*O*-rutinoside in citrus nectar. Orange blossom nectar was analysed by HPLC-MSn and hesperetin 7-rutinoside (hesperidin) was the main flavonoid present (Fig. 2). Thus, it is expected that this compound could be present in orange blossom honey. However, the presence of this compound in rosemary honey is something unexpected, as previous analysis of rosemary nectar did not show the presence of flavanones suggesting that the presence of **11** in the analysed rosemary honey samples could be due to contamination with orange nectar.

Quercetin diglycosides, such as quercetin-3-*O*-sophoroside (**2**) and quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside (**10**), were only detected in significant quantifiable amounts in rapeseed and canola honeys respectively. The 8-methoxykaempferol glycosides, either the 3-*O*-

sophoroside or the -3-*O*-neohesperidoside (**4**, **5**), were detected in canola, cherry blossom, and in one eucalyptus sample, and in minor proportions in lucerne and rapeseed honeys. However, **5**, has only been detected in canola and in traces in rapeseed honey. These results keep showing a close relationship between canola and rapeseed honeys. The presence of **4** in only one sample of cherry blossom and eucalyptus honey could be consistent with a contamination with pollen flavonoids, as this flavonoid was found as the main pigment in almond and other Rosaceae pollens. [24]

Kaempferol diglycoside derivatives (**3**, **6**, **8**, and **12**) have been detected in most honey samples analyzed in this study. Nevertheless, **3** and **6** have been detected in higher proportions in rapeseed honey (Table 3). Kaempferol-3-*O*-sophoroside (**6**) has also been observed in smaller amounts in all the orange and rosemary honeys analysed, as well as in two of the linden honeys studied. Compound **8** was previously identified as a relevant constituent in rosemary nectar [11]. On the other hand, in this study kaempferol-3-*O*-neohesperidoside (**8**) was detected in cherry blossom, rhododendron and taraxacum honeys.

Isorhamnetin diglycosides, such as compounds **7**, **9** and **13**, have been detected in many of the samples analysed. Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-sophoroside (**7**) was only identified in rapeseed, Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-gentiobioside (**13**) was identified in canola, sunflowers and rapeseed samples, in trace amounts in the last case. It is interesting that isorhamnetin 3-*O*-neohesperidoside (**9**) was present in all the tilia honey samples analysed, and this could be an appropriate floral marker that should be further studied in the future. Moreover, this compound was too detected in cherry blossom, rapeseed, and rhododendron.

The different eucalyptus honey samples analyzed showed an inconsistent flavonoid glycoside pattern, and this was surprising as in previous studies we had

demonstrated the presence of specific markers for this honey type including the flavonoids myricetin, tricetin and luteolin [19,20]. In addition, the presence of hesperetin glycosides in orange and rosemary honeys is also inconsistent with the previous suggestion of hesperetin as marker of the floral origin of citrus honey. By this reason, a study of the flavonoid glycosides present in eucalyptus and orange floral nectars using HPLC-MSn is necessary to confirm the relevance of these analyses in the determination of the floral origin of honey.

3.3. *Flavonoid glycosides in eucalyptus nectar.*

The occurrence of characteristic markers in eucalyptus honey was reported in a study of eucalyptus honeys, where myricetin, tricetin and luteolin were detected [19,20]. These flavonoids were not detected in any other unifloral honey analyzed [9]. However, these markers were not confirmed with the analysis of eucalyptus nectar, as nectar collection in this case was not an easy task, due to the location of flowers high in the trees and to the small amount of nectar produced. In the present study, eucalyptus nectar could be directly collected from eucalyptus blossom. The chromatogram at 340 nm of eucalyptus nectar showed different compounds with UV spectra characteristic of flavonols (Fig. 3). The MS/MS study showed the presence of different diglycosides, monoglycosides and aglycones of flavonoids (Table 4). The floral markers, myricetin (3,5,7,3',4',5'-hexahydroxyflavone) (**25**), tricetin (5,7,4'-trihydroxy-3',5'-dimethoxyflavone) (**27**), luteolin (5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavone) (**28**) and their diglucosides (sophorosides; glucosyl(1→2) glucosides) were detected in the nectar chromatogram (Fig. 3). Moreover, other flavonoids as quercetin, kaempferol, and isorhamnetin glycosides were also detected in this nectar.

The MS²[M-H]⁻ fragmentation of compounds **18**, **20** and **22** shows in all cases a loss of a glucosyl residue (loss of 162 m.u.) and/or a glucosyl residue +H₂O (loss of 180 m.u.) (Table 4). These intermediate ions suggest an interglycosidic linkage 1→2 (glucose: [M-H-162]⁻/[M-H-180]⁻). Then these flavonoids could be tentatively identified as sophoroside derivatives (glucosyl (1→2) glucoside) (Table 4) [21]. In the MS-MS analyses of compounds **10**, **12** and **26** intermediate fragments were not observed suggesting an interglycosidic linkage 1→6 (rutinoside; rhamnosyl (1→6) glucoside) [26]. This indicates that **10** is quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside, **12**, kaempferol-3-*O*-rutinoside and **26** isorhamnetin-7-*O*-rutinoside. The MS spectra of **19** and **21**, show the presence of only one fragment [M-H-162]⁻ as base peak indicating that these flavonoid diglycosides were glycosylated at two different phenolic hydroxyls of the flavonoid nucleus [23]. These compounds could be probably identified as myricetin-3,7-di-*O*-glucoside and tricetin-3,4'-di-*O*-glucoside respectively. Compounds **29** and **30** were detected in trace amounts and they have been tentatively characterized as pentosyl-hexosides of myricetin and tricetin respectively. Moreover, the monoglycosides **23** and **24** were identified as quercetin-3-glucuronide and tricetin-7-glucoside respectively (Table 4).

3.4. *Flavonoid compounds in eucalyptus honey.*

The extracts of eucalyptus honey were analyzed by HPLC-DAD-MSⁿ (Fig. 4). The flavonoids myricetin (**25**), tricetin (**27**) and luteolin (**28**) were detected in all the eucalyptus honey samples analysed, as describe above. The flavonoid glycosides detected in nectar, were not detected in honey. In a previous work, these flavonoid aglycones were suggested as floral markers for eucalyptus honey [19, 20]. Tricetin and luteolin were the main flavonoids detected in the extracts of these eucalyptus honey samples (Table 3 and Fig. 4). Moreover, quercetin (**Q**) and kaempferol (**K**) were also

detected in the eucalyptus honeys included in this study (Fig. 4). These results are fully in agreement with previous studies on European eucalyptus honeys [19]. However, quercetin and kaempferol were not detected as glucosides in the eucalyptus nectar analysed. Therefore, these two flavonoids should not be used as markers for this floral origin, as they are common honey flavonoids found in many other unifloral honeys [9].

4. Discussion and conclusion

This study reveals that flavonoid glycosides are common constituents in honey. They are mainly glycosides of the flavonols quercetin, kaempferol, isorhamnetin and 8-methoxykaempferol although other less common flavonoids, as is the case of flavanones in citrus honey, are also present in specific floral origins. This means that specific flavonoid markers could be found in other honeys. The most frequent glycosidic combinations include rhamnosyl-hexosides (rutinosides and neohesperidosides) and rhamnosides, but dihexosides are also very frequent, particularly sophorosides.

Eucalyptus honey deserves a special comment, as this honey is particularly poor in flavonoid glycosides, although the flavonoids aglycones myricetin, tricetin and luteolin were found to be good markers for this type of honey [19, 20]. This can be explained after the analysis of eucalyptus blossom nectar, as this contains mainly myricetin, tricetin and luteolin sophorosides, that can be readily hydrolyzed by the bee saliva glucosidases, this being the reason why the aglycones are the main metabolites occurring in honey. On the contrary, nectars rich in rhamnosyl-glucosides (rutinosides or neohesperidosides), that are not hydrolyzed by the bee saliva enzymes, lead to honeys with high amounts of flavonoid glycosides, as is the case of Robinia honey

recently published [22] and is also the case of citrus honey (flavanone-rutinoside) and canola and rapeseed honeys that contain relatively high content of flavonoid glycosides.

These results also show that characteristic flavonoid glycoside patterns are found in specific floral origins, and that these findings are quite consistent within a specific floral origin. Thus, a larger number of honey samples from specific floral origins should be analyzed using HPLC-MSn in the future, in order to validate the use of this promising analytical method for the determination of the floral origin of honey.

5. Acknowledgements

This work has been funded by the European Commission; project Beeshop, FOOD CT-2006-022568. The authors are grateful to Dr. L. Bortolotti and Dr. A.G. Sabatini from Bologna CRA-APII (Italy) and Dr. J. Simuth from University (Slovakia) for providing honey unifloral honey samples.

6. References

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Table 1. Honey samples.

	Samples	Floral origin	Location
1	Canola	<i>Brassica napus</i>	Bologna – Italy
2	Cherry blossom –1	<i>Prunus avium</i>	Frossaco – Italy
3	Cherry blossom– 2	<i>Prunus avium</i>	Tornareccio-CH (Italy)
4	Eucalyptus – 1	<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i>	Roma – Italy
5	Eucalyptus – 2	<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp	CI – Spain
6	Eucalyptus – 3	<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp	MK – Spain
7	Eucalyptus – 4	<i>Eucalyptus</i> spp	Callosa Segura – Spain
8	Linden – 1	<i>Tilia</i> spp	Sebecheleby – Slovakia
9	Linden – 2	<i>Tilia</i> spp	Bratislava – Slovakia
10	Linden – 3	<i>Tilia</i> spp	Banská – Slovakia
11	Lucerne – 1	<i>Mendicago sativa</i>	Bologna – Italy
12	Lucerne – 2	<i>Mendicago sativa</i>	Bologna – Italy
13	Lavander	<i>Lavandula</i> spp	Puimoisson – Italy
14	Orange Blossom – 2	<i>Citrus</i> spp.	Roccascalegna-CH – Italy
15	Orange Blossom – 2	<i>Citrus</i> spp.	Tornareccio- CH – Italy
16	Rapeseed	<i>Rapessed</i> (<i>Brassica campestris</i>)	Sebechleby –Slovakia
17	Rhododendron – 1	<i>Rhododendron</i> spp	Brescia – Italy
18	Rosemary – 1	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Tornareccio- CH – Italy
19	Rosemary – 2	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Manfredonia-FG – Italy
20	Sunflower	<i>Heliamtus annus</i>	Bologna – Italy
21	Taraxacum – 1	<i>Taraxacum officinalis</i>	Bologna – Italy
22	Taraxacum – 2	<i>Taraxacum officinalis</i>	Rivolta d’ Adda – Italy

23	Tilia – 1	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Bologna – Italy
24	Tilia – 2	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Minerbio - BO – Italy
25	Tilia – 3	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Torino – Italy
26	Tilia – 4	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Bologna – Italy
27	Tilia – 5	<i>Tilia ssp</i>	Bologna – Italy

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Figure 1. HPLC-DAD chromatogram (340 nm) of selected unifloral honey. **(A)** Canola, **(B)** Cherry Blossom – 2, **(C)** Eucalyptus – 2, **(D)** Lucerne, **(E)** Orange – 2, **(F)** Rapessed, **(G)** Rhododendron, **(H)** Rosemary – 1, **(I)** Sunflowers – 1, **(J)** Taraxacum – 2, **(K)** Tilia1 **(1)** Isorhamnetin -3-*O*-(pentosyl-hexoside)-7-*O*-hexoside; **(2)** Quercetin-3-*O*-sophoroside; **(3)** Kaempferol-3,4'-di-*O*-hexoside; **(4)** 8-Methoxykaempferol-3-*O*-sophoroside; **(5)** 8-Methoxykaempferol -3-*O*-neoheperidoside; **(6)** Kaempferol-3-*O*-sophoroside; **(7)** Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-sophoroside; **(8)** Kaempferol-3-*O*- neoheperidoside; **(9)** Isorhamnetin -3-*O*- neoheperidoside; **(10)** Quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside; **(11)** Hesperidin; **(12)** Kaempferol-3-*O*-rutinoside; **(13)** Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-gentiobioside; **(14)** Isorhamnetin-3-*O*-rutinoside-7-*O*-glucoside; **(15)** Quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside-7-*O*-rhamnoside; **(16)** Kaempferol-3-*O*-sophoroside-7-*O*-rhamnoside; **(17)** Kaempferol-3-*O*-rutinoside-7-*O*-rhamnoside; (ABA) Abscisic acid; (OH₁) *p*-Coumaric acid; (OH₂) Ferulic acid; (OH₃) and (OH₄) Hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives.

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28 **Figure 2.** HPLC-DAD chromatogram (290 nm) of orange nectar. **(11)** Hesperidin.

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32 **Figure 3.** HPLC-DAD chromatogram (340 nm) of eucalyptus nectar. (18) Myricetin-3-
33 *O*-sophoroside; (19) Myricetin-3,7-di-*O*-glucoside; (20) Tricetin-7-*O*-sophoroside; (21)
34 Tricetin-7,4'-di-*O*-glucoside; (22) Luteolin-7-*O*-sophoroside; (23) Quercetin-3-*O*-
35 glucuronide; (10) Quercetin-3-*O*-rutinoside; (24) Tricetin-7-*O*- glucoside; (25)
36 Myricetin; (12) Kaempferol-7-*O*-rutinoside; (26) Isorhamnetin-7-*O*-rutinoside; (27)
37 Tricetin; (28) Luteolin; (29) Myricetin-3-*O*-(pentosyl-glucoside); (30) Tricetin-7-*O*-
38 (pentosyl-glucoside).

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44 **Figure 4.** HPLC-DAD chromatogram (340 nm) of eucalyptus honey. **(2)** Myricetin-3,7-
45 di-*O*-glucoside; **(25)** Myricetin; **(27)** Tricetin; **(28)** Luteolin (Q) Quercetin; (K),
46 Kaempferol; (Pb), Pinobanksin (3,5,7-trihydroxyflavanone); (Pc), Pinocembrin (5,7-
47 dihydroxyflavanone); (Ch), Chrysin (5,7-dihydroxyflavone); (G), Galangin (3,5,7-
48 trihydroxyflavone); (Dm), Dimethyl-allyl-caffeate; (Fe), Phenyl-ethyl caffeate; Tch
49 (Techochrysin) (5-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavone).

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